

BELMONT
FORUM

FAPESP
FUNDAÇÃO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA
DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO

AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA RECHERCHE
ANR

Dataset compatibility: WDPA

CESAB
CENTRE FOR THE SYNTHESIS AND ANALYSIS
OF BIODIVERSITY

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PARSEC is a project sponsored by the Belmont Forum as part of its Collaborative Research Action (CRA) on Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI), with funding from FAPESP, the ANR, JST and the NSF, with collaborators from Australia, and support from the synthesis centre CESAB of the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity.

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Steps to accountability

Can we rely on the WDPA for our purposes across countries?

- Countries supply the data to the WDPA for standardisation across the globe – this is our potential analytical advantage
- BUT we are making within-country training decisions about the effect of a PA on adjacent communities using within-country data...so the reality is when, how big, what usage (IUCN I, II...VI) and what shape the PAs actually are.

Does the WDPA supply this and if not, what adjustments should be made to ensure the best detection of affect.

Origin of WDPA data

country	in-country data collation	how created	link to WDPA	in-country real time
Australia	CAPAD (Collaborative Australian Protected Areas Database)	each state collects data and sends biannually to DAWE (the federal environment department) where the separate data sets are collated according to WDPA criteria	Spatial data (polygons in ESRI geodatabase format) which has an 'attribute table' with the text data of each protected area is sent to the WDPA periodically.	updated every 2 years
USA	PAD-US	Each state collects data, using core attributes defined by USGS, then submitted for cleaning.		
Brazil	CNUC (Cadastro Nacional de Unidades de Conservação)	The CNUC is updated continuously within-country	The CNUC from MMA ('Ministério de Meio Ambiente') updates the WDPA when requested	It seems not to be periodical or even automatically

Australia

World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA)
Year: 2022
11,149 Total Protected Areas

Unit: Polygon

Australian Government

[Collaborative Australian Protected Areas Database \(CAPAD\)](#)
Year: 2020
11,426 Total Protected Areas

Unit: Polygon

Difference in number of PAs by census unit

SA2

difference between WDPA and CAPAD area
(% CAPAD area)

Difference in area of PAs by ecoregion

Difference in PAs for selected affected towns

Protected areas in Brazil

Law n.º 9.985, de 18 de julho de 2000

Brazil

WDPA

WDPA distribution by IUCN category

MMA

MMA distribution by IUCN category

Brazil

WDPA

WDPA distribution

MMA

MMA distribution

Protected areas in Brazil

Two groups

Full protection – with the purpose of preserving nature, being admitted only the indirect use of natural resources, and therefore the rules and norms are restrictive

Sustainable use - conciliates the conservation of nature with the sustainable use of part of the natural resources

Full protection (IUCN I, II, III)

- Ecological Station
- Biological Reserve
- National Park
- Wildlife Refuge
- Natural Monument

Sustainable use (IUCN IV, V, VI)

- Environmental Protection Area
- Area of Relevant Ecological Interest
- National Forest
- Extractive Reserve
- Fauna Reserve
- Sustainable Development Reserve
- Private Reserve of Natural Heritage

Brazilian Protected Areas Panel

CNUC 2022

- Accessible
- Visually queries and presentation
- Updated continuously
- Portuguese
- organisation not all that clear

CNUC 2022 (october)

PI	Total
Ecological Station	99
Natural Monument	69
Park	478
Wildlife Refuge	87
Biological Reserve	62
Total	795

SU	Total
Environmental Protection Area	386
Area of Relevant Ecological Interest	79
Forest	101
Sustainable Development Reserve	39
Extractive Reserve	96
Private Reserve of Natural Heritage	650
Total	1351

In the shapefile - 2146

In the website – 2659

WDPA 2022 (april)

IUCN I, II, III	Total
Ecological Station	92
Natural Monument	54
Park	397
Wildlife Refuge	71
Biological Reserve	59
Ramsar Site, Wetland of Int. Importance	7
Total	680
IUCN IV, V, VI	Total
Environmental Protection Area	310
Area of Relevant Ecological Interest	50
Forest	99
Sustainable Development Reserve	38
Extractive Reserve	93
Private Reserve of Natural Heritage	553
Historic Site and Cultural Heritage	1
Ramsar Site, Wetland of Int. Importance	3
Total	1147
Not reported / Not applicable	Total
Indigenous Area	3
Indigenous Reserve	19
Indigenous Land	697
World Heritage Site (natural or mixed)	7
Ramsar Site, Wetland of Int. Importance	10
Total	736

Total 2563

commentary

Visconti, P., et al. 2013. Effects of Errors and Gaps in Spatial Data Sets on Assessment of Conservation Progress: Errors and Gaps in Spatial Data Sets. *Conservation Biology* 27, 1000–1010.

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<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1813323115>

Elsen, P.R., et al. 2018. Reply to You et al.: The World Database on Protected Areas is an invaluable resource for global conservation assessments and planning. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 115.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1813791115>

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<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0869-38/S>

Moudrý, V., Devillers, R., 2020. Quality and usability challenges of global marine biodiversity databases: An example for marine mammal data. *Ecological Informatics* 56, 101051.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2020.101051>

Effects of Errors and Gaps in Spatial Data Sets on Assessment of Conservation Progress

P. VISCONTI,*† M. DI MARCO,* ‡ J. G. ÁLVAREZ-ROMERO,† S. R. JANUCHOWSKI-HARTLEY,†‡ R. L. PRESSEY,† R. WEEKS,† AND C. RONDININI*

*Global Mammal Assessment Program, Department of Biology and Biotechnologies, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome 00185, Italy
†Australian Research Council Centre of Excellence for Coral Reef Studies, James Cook University, Townsville, Queensland 4811, Australia

‡Center for Limnology, 680 N. Park Street, University of Wisconsin-Madison, Madison, WI 53705, USA

Pitfall of big databases

Zhangqiang You*, Junhua Hu^{h1}, Qing Wei*, Chunwang Li*, Xiaofei Deng*, and Zhigang Jian;

Now, more and more studies use big databases, such as the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) (<https://www.protectedplanet.net/>), which is now a predominant source of information on world protected areas (PAs) (1–4). In PNAS, Elsen et al. (5) report that mountain ranges in Africa and Asia had the lowest elevational protection, based on analyses of the WDPA database. We suspect that this may not be true. China is a mountainous country in Asia (Fig. 1A) (5); we analyzed the elevational protection by China's National Nature Reserve (CNNR) and found that higher elevations

Elsen et al. (5), with clear divergent Asia, considering different categories besides national nature reserves, and county nature reserves were established (mep.gov.cn/gkml/hbb/bwj/201611.htm). This obviously differs from the 1). Other Asian countries most likely problem. Such a pitfall must be not nationists and managers, as the trend database for authoritative information

Sixty years of tracking conservation progress using the World Database on Protected Areas

Heather C. Bingham¹*, Diego Juffe Bignoli², Edward Lewis¹, Brian MacSharry^{1,2}, N. Piero Visconti^{3,4,5}, Marine Deguignet¹, Murielle Misrachi¹, Matt Walpole⁶, Jessica L. Thomas M. Brooks⁷ and Naomi Kingston¹

The world's protected area network is constantly changing, and the dynamics of this network are tracked by the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA). This database evolved from a list of protected areas first mapped by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) in 1959, and it now informs the key indicators that track progress toward area-based conservation goals. The WDPA illuminates the role of protected areas in advancing a range of international objectives including the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Sustainable Development Goals. Despite ongoing challenges such as a complex global dataset, the WDPA is continuously improving and taking advantage of new data to be widely applicable to diverse users, including those in sectors far from its original intended audience. In the future, it will expand to include areas that contribute to conservation and sustainable use outside of formal protected areas, and increasingly link to other key global datasets. These innovations in the way the WDPA is managed and knowledge to support a sustainable future for biodiversity and people globally.

REPLY TO YOU ET AL.:

The World Database on Protected Areas is an invaluable resource for global conservation assessments and planning

Paul R. Elsen¹, William B. Monahan², and Adina M. Merenlender³

In their Letter, You et al. (1) raise concerns about the use of the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) (<https://www.protectedplanet.net/>) in conservation assessments and planning. Their concern arises from potential differences in protected area (PA) delineations and designations between the WDPA and alternate, national PA datasets, citing China's National Nature Reserves (CNNR) as an example with apparent deviations. You et al. (1) highlight that using the CNNR in calculations of elevational protection yields results that contrast with those published in our original paper (2).

assessments of meeting conservation targets, we echo You et al.'s (1) call for conservation practitioners to carefully consider the data sources appropriate for the geographic scope of interest, and to use the best available data for their particular application. Our study of the global protection of elevational gradients (2) required the use of a global PA dataset to minimize biases in comparisons across mountainous regions. As You et al. (1) correctly point out, the WDPA is the authoritative dataset for international PA delineations and designations that follows globally consistent standards, is regularly validated, and is continuously

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Thankyou

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